
155. The Gaia satellite operations

TEN YEARS ON from the launch of Gaia, 19 December 2013, I provide a summary of the tasks involved in the operations of the Gaia satellite. I will start with a brief background to some of the top-level requirements that influenced the operational design and implementation.

PREPARATIONS FOR THE operations of a mission like Gaia start many years before launch. Factors like the chosen orbit location, the ambient environment including thermal stability, incident radiation and gravitational torques, telemetry rate, and many others, feed into the requirements. Early planning sets in progress the ground segment development and pre-launch activities, and later the launch, instrument commissioning, and eventually the routine operational phase, all with the objectives of keeping the mission operational, safe, and optimised over its target mission duration.

A small operations support team, at ESOC, was closely involved from the very earliest days of the project's development around 1997, helping to select the target orbit, ground-segment requirements, the need for station keeping manoeuvres, and so on, eventually leading to the Ground Segment Requirements Review.

AT ITS CHOSEN orbit location, the Sun–Earth Lagrange point L2, varying between 1.2–1.8 Mkm from Earth, Gaia has an unobscured view of the sky, and occupies a stable thermal environment. Disadvantages of L2 include a greater launch mass, more challenging space–ground communications, and ‘station-keeping manoeuvres’ (a few tens of cm/sec every 1–2 months) required to keep the satellite in its (unstable equilibrium) orbit. And at the end of its mission, reserve fuel will be used to de-orbit Gaia from L2 into interplanetary space, keeping the L2 region clear for future missions.

Spacecraft operated at L2 (in the past WMAP, Herschel, Planck and today including JWST) have quasi-periodic orbits with amplitudes of typically several 100 000 km. Even within this vast volume of space, operators share their orbital data and coordinate, so there is essentially no risk of a collision!

GAIA USES the ESTRACK 35-m ground station network, ESA's ground infrastructure for science and deep space missions. At the time of Gaia's launch, there were three available stations located more or less evenly around the Earth in longitude (Spain, Australia, South America), from each of which Gaia is visible for about 8 hr per day. Gaia remains the heaviest user of these stations out of all ESA's missions. Even with a relatively high data rate of 10 Mbps (downlinked via the phased array antenna, at X-band), and optimised onboard data compression, the volume of data to be downloaded requires, on average, two long passes per day.

The round-trip communication time, around 10 s, has no major operational consequences: Gaia was designed to be autonomous: queued commands are up-linked, but often not executed for several hours.

GAIA HAS several attitude control modes, from the simplest ‘safe mode’ (with only essential units active in case of anomalies), all the way up to the ‘normal mode’ in which the satellite is scanning the celestial sphere following its pre-defined ‘nominal scanning law’.

Coarse pointing information is obtained from a star tracker and an advanced gyro system. Attitude control is performed using conventional thrusters used only occasionally to adjust and maintain the orbit, and specially designed very low-level (micro-Newton) cold-gas thrusters. These are used to semi-continuously ‘nudge’ the satellite to follow its desired scanning law, based on spin rate measurements obtained from the star images passing across the focal plane ‘sky mappers’.

The satellite has no moving parts: the micro-Newton thrusters are used almost entirely to compensate for the photon pressure of sunlight incident on the 2000 kg spacecraft. For the time-delay integration (TDI) read-out of the instrument's focal plane CCDs to operate correctly, without image smearing, the satellite rotation rate has to be managed extremely precisely. The rotation rate has to be controlled to within 0.1 milli-arcsec per second... this rate error would take about 400 years to build up to a full rotation!

FROM AROUND 2008, the Mission Operations Team began to grow as the task of putting the operational ground segment together started to ramp up. A handful of mission-dedicated engineers, forming the Flight Control Team, worked with some part-time support from specialist areas (such as ground stations, flight dynamics, and mission data systems), taking the ground segment 'system-level requirements' to the next level of detail, and defining the subsystem specifications.

While many of these aspects are quite standard across different missions, dedicated development effort was required for the high data rates, and the unprecedented time correlation accuracy. In the years preceding launch, the ground segment was built up progressively, and tested against the spacecraft as it was assembled.

There were a few key tests, each of a few weeks duration, where the operations team had to verify that they could both properly decode the satellite data, and were able to command and control it. A parallel effort, in close collaboration with the scientific teams, was required to verify that all of the data required for the on-ground analysis was properly included and appropriately formatted in the highly complex telemetry stream.

In the last months before launch, the operational validation stage started: the 'team of teams' was put through a rigorous simulation campaign. As well as staff covering the main operational disciplines in ESOC, the 'team of teams' also included experts from the Gaia project team at ESTEC, and from the industrial consortium (mainly the prime contractor Airbus Defence & Space) who constructed and assembled the satellite.

In practice, the Mission Operations Team operated from the main control room at ESOC, and rehearsed, repeatedly, for the flight phases, focusing on the critical operations. They used the actual flight procedures and mission control system connected to a computer simulator which, like the real satellite, could be commanded, and which could generate appropriate telemetry.

After testing the 'nominal' scenarios, various problems, unknown to the operations team, were injected into the system. Their task was to figure out how to fix the problems. As David Milligan said in my interview with him: *'It was tough at the time, but it was very useful, and a lot of fun looking back.'*

AFTER LAUNCH, ESOC took control of the spacecraft as it separated from the upper stage of the launch vehicle. During the first hour or so after separation the spacecraft performed, autonomously, the first critical activities, essentially putting it into a safe and stable state, switching on the transmitter for contact with the ground, preparing a number of critical subsystems (e.g. the chemical propulsion subsystem) ready for use, establishing attitude control, and orienting the solar panels toward the Sun.

Then the 10-m diameter sunshield was deployed, a particularly tense sequence due to its complex design. This was also a particularly time-critical phase, since the satellite was running only on internal battery power throughout the launch phase. And by the time Gaia separated from the Soyuz launch vehicle, roughly one third of the battery power had already been used. By the end of the deployment sequence, Gaia was expected to have used another third, so that very little time would be available to correct for any malfunctions. As a result, this phase was rehearsed intensively, with contingency procedures established for all sorts of potential problems. *'Despite all the work going into these contingency procedures, it was actually a good feeling when we didn't need to use them'*, Milligan said.

THE GROUND SEGMENT continued the task of 'waking Gaia up' from its initial very basic state. Higher level units were switched on, checked out, and made ready for the more complex operations to follow.

The first important task was to correct and fine tune the navigational course to L2, because the initial trajectory provided by the launcher invariably requires some adjustment. Referred to as the 'day 2 manoeuvre', this adjustment could not be delayed by much, otherwise it would not be possible to reach the operational orbit.

To execute this, Gaia needed to go into a more complex attitude mode, allowing knowledge of its pointing in all three dimensions. At spacecraft level, the star tracker was activated, then put it into the autonomous control loop. In the meantime, the radiometric data (Doppler and range data from the radio frequency link) was being used to compute Gaia's precise position and velocity in space.

Once the trajectory was well established, the operations team could work out how to program the on-board chemical thrusters to correct the trajectory in the required way. On day two, they fired the engines for around 25 minutes, making a suitable correction, and putting Gaia perfectly on-course for the L2 region.

Overall, these few days of critical LEOP (Launch and Early Orbit Phase) operations went smoothly, although there were a few unexpected events to deal with. One was a payload mirror heater behaving bizarrely, in a way that didn't make sense in terms of its temperature. They quickly figured that a heater and thermistor had been wrongly wired together (i.e. the system was reading the temperature on one mirror, but switching the heater on/off on another mirror). Within a few hours, after patching the software, the problem was fixed.

In another incident, after switching on the cold gas system they saw that the tanks were reading zero pressure, suggesting that they were empty! But they figured out that a pressure transducer had tripped off and was giving a false reading... to some sighs of relief.

WITH THE successful Launch and Early Orbit Phase completed, the operations team vacated the main control room at ESOC, and moved to a smaller dedicated control room, and with a lot fewer people. And the intensive 24-hour ground station coverage was no longer required.

ON THE TRANSFER of the satellite to L2, the operations team were switching on, and checking out, the more complex units and functions needed for its science operations. There were many activities, but they were less time critical. Starting with the spacecraft ‘platform’ (providing the support function to the instruments themselves) bespoke items such as the micro propulsion system, or the specially designed phased-array antenna, had to be carefully activated. Expert analysis was required to confirm that they were working as expected.

Sometimes, sequences had to wait until there was enough power available to test them. For example, in the early part of the transfer to L2, a lot of power was still routed to telescope decontamination heating. And only when this was ramped down was there enough power available to switch on the phased-array antenna, and check its performance.

As the operations team gained confidence in the performance, some activities could be put in the ‘time-tagged’ queue, to be executed when the satellite was not in contact with ground. For a few days after launch, full-time contact was maintained, but during commissioning, daily contact was more like 12 hours per day – the stations that Gaia used are all a shared resource, and other missions need them too. With the use of the ‘time tagged queue’, commanding activities could continue even when not in contact with the ground and, in this way, quite a lot was achieved before arriving at L2. The main barriers to starting an activity were often constraints like the availability of power, or the temperatures being cool enough in the telescope.

A further orbital manoeuvre was carried out 28 days after launch. This ‘L2 insertion burn’ was much bigger, with the thrusters operating for a total of more than 100 minutes, about 80% of what was finally need. The final insertion was executed a few days later.

Perfectly placed in L2, the several months of commissioning the payload began. Early tasks included fine-tuning the mirror focus, adjusting many parameters in the seven payload video processing units (the most powerful computers on Gaia), and making several iterative adjustments to the satellite’s rotation rate.

In practice, the Gaia spacecraft has a number of deeply interconnected subsystems. For example, for the telescope to work correctly, the spacecraft rotation rate must be precisely controlled, while the instrument itself feeds the rate measurement back into the AOCS (attitude and orbit control system) rotational control loop.

In the early phases of mission planning, commissioning was foreseen to require three months. As launch approached, this increased to 4.5 months. The last commissioning plan produced a few weeks before launch extended this to 5 months. The numerous adjustments required in practice meant that ESOC eventually scheduled six months from launch to the end of commissioning to get everything working optimally.

EVERYTHING WAS GOING very well and morale was high, but by January–February 2014, a slow accumulation of problems started accumulating, and the overall picture changed.

As the operations team began testing the payload in more detail some unexpected problems appeared. One was that the laser in the ‘basic angle monitoring’ device (an onboard laser interferometer which measures precisely the angle between the two main telescope mirrors) seemed to be dimming over time. But this was not a problem with the laser, because the star images were also dimming.

It slowly became clear that the mirrors were ‘clouding over’, most likely by water ice. This meant that the program of decontamination heating performed in the initial weeks had not been enough. They could confirm this by running the decontamination procedures again and switching the heaters back on. Straight away the stars and laser were brighter and clearer.

Around this time the operations team also noticed the background light (or straylight) was too high. Could the two problems be connected? The water ice inside the telescope interior, which should be dark, was perhaps reflecting light. Then two further problems appeared: a micro propulsion thruster started to malfunction, and furthermore the telescope ‘basic angle’, the angle between the two fields of view, was varying far more than had been predicted.

As David Milligan recalls: *‘For a month or two it felt like for every problem we’d solve, another two would pop up. As these issues mounted, there was some time with genuine doubts as to whether the mission could achieve all the scientific goals’.*

THE THREE big telescope problems – ice, straylight and telescope instability – required much thought and attention. In space operations there is only the telemetry to look at, and everything has to be deduced from those data.

For the telescope problems there were a number of theories. There was a suspicion that the ice and straylight were linked. While this was a favourite theory for a while, it was hard to prove, and correspondingly hard to fix. The theory was that the inside of the telescope roof was also getting covered in ice. The roof could not easily be decontaminated since there were no heaters there.

BUT THERE WAS also an idea to fix these problems simultaneously, by deliberately turning the spacecraft, and allowing sunlight to enter into the telescope tent. To do so would require over-riding the on-board safety protections. This required considerable analysis, not least because substantial effort had been invested in building safeguards on-board to ensure the Sun never shone directly into the telescope tent, or field of view.

The danger was that if something went wrong, like going slightly too far, or something unexpectedly nudging the satellite in the wrong direction, sunlight could hit the cameras and do serious and probably irreversible damage. It was a contentious idea, and some resisted it strongly. In terms of risk/reward it just seemed too soon to attempt something so risky. And if it proved really necessary, a lot of operational ground testing would be required in order to perform the operation as safely as possible.

In the end the operations team came up with a compromise: they would get more evidence both from on-board, but also on ground. On-board they would perform some experimental attitudes and rotations to get more data, whilst in parallel, on the ground, some laboratory tests would be performed.

In laboratory testing, measurements would be made to show exactly how reflective a small layer of ice would be on the inside of the payload tent. Whilst this was ongoing, an operational campaign was initiated to design and test procedures to let sunlight into the tent as safely as possible.

THIS ALL LED to some new forms of operating the satellite being developed, such as operating in a standard sky-scanning mode, but with a larger inclination between the spin axis and the Sun direction, in an attempt to vary the amount of sunlight incident on the internal payload baffles.

Along with some interesting results, there were further problems. In one of the tests, a guidance problem caused the on-board computer to be confused about where it should be pointing, and it went into 'safe mode', switching almost everything off, and going back to a similar state as it was when it initially separated the launcher.

It was also immediately clear that it had not entered a 'normal' safe mode, but close to what had been designated as the 'last-chance' safe mode. Lengthy investigations identified that there had been another failure: a chemical thruster used for attitude control in the safe mode, actually the 'redundant' one to be used in case of serious problems, was not functioning.

This also meant that the safe mode was itself compromised, being no long 'single-failure tolerant', and therefore significant attention now had to focus on that most critical aspect.

This was one of the project's 'lowest points' in commissioning because of the many problems that had to be addressed in parallel, several of them serious without immediately obvious solutions. Progress came through hard work, long hours, and great teamwork from everyone involved: at ESOC, with the prime contractor Airbus Defence & Space and some of their sub-contractors, with the project team in ESTEC, in test laboratories, and contributions from the scientific consortium, DPAC.

THE SAFE MODE ISSUE was solved by an ingenious re-programming of which thrusters are used in safe mode. This involved using some that had not been foreseen for attitude control, but would contribute because they had some ability to turn the spacecraft, as well as their normal function of providing orbital change thrusts. This took some months to complete, since changing 'survival software' was not something that could be rushed, and it required extensive testing.

The results from the experiments to understand the payload issues then started to come through one by one. It became evident that all of the three telescope problems were proportional to the solar aspect angle. The on-ground laboratory test results meanwhile showed that a thin layer of ice on the inside of the payload tent would actually make the straylight problems better, not worse! So, with that somewhat counter-intuitive result, the combined 'straylight and ice' theory was gone, and with it the idea of allowing more sunlight into the telescope as a fix.

It was also found from ground experiments that the edge of the sunshield was brighter than predicted due to some protruding fibres diffracting light. With the straylight origin now understood, certain software changes were designed to better handle the problem, and they were applied to the on-board payload computers in the following months.

TO ADDRESS the build-up of ice, a sequence of decontamination operations was designed. Time would have to be assigned to this, interrupting the routine mission operations, but it became clear that the impact would be manageable, and would improve with time.

The extra decontamination activities, each run requiring some two weeks out of normal operations, were needed in the commissioning phase, and further into the early routine phase. Over the years the trapped air (and therefore water vapour) has slowly dissipated. Indeed, the situation has been stable now for several years, and probably no further decontamination activities will be needed.

LASTLY WAS THE ISSUE of the telescope 'basic angle' stability. Extensive characterisation demonstrated that, although it was much less stable than had been de-

signed, it was oscillating in a predictable and measurable way. So the answer was to take the variations into account in the data processing. It would not be easy for the data processing team, but it was nevertheless considered possible to account for in principle.

Commissioning was declared completed by July 2014. And it is worth underlining that, despite the various problems encountered and described here, most of the systems were functioning extremely well.

IN FACT, another challenge that the operations team faced was due to the excellent performance of the entire payload. This meant that Gaia was able to observe fainter stars than had been originally planned, which meant in turn that much more data than originally planned needed to be sent down from the satellite if this additional scientific bounty was not to be lost.

It turned out that there was enough capacity in the ground stations to schedule the additional time required to download the data from the satellite during the available passes. But the Spacecraft Control ('Spacon') team, the shift workers who operate the satellite, was consequently too small. Two shifts per day would be needed, and sometimes three, instead of one. Even assuming an increased budget to pay for a larger team, it would require months to recruit and train them. And, in the meantime, much additional data would be lost.

The operations team soon established a way to automate these extra passes, and downlink the data without the spacecraft control team in place. Back in 2014 this was not part of standard procedures, and required use of some of the new automation technologies that were becoming available, both onboard and on ground. One of the components was a small on-board (software) procedure which would allow the spacecraft to understand if a ground station was currently in contact. If contact was lost, the spacecraft would automatically stop downlinking the data to ground.

Before these new operations were put in place, the undersized 'Spacon' team covered more shifts than originally planned, greatly assisting the additional data recovery. The new procedures allowed some 30–40% more data to be telemetered to ground than originally foreseen, helping to make the resulting scientific data releases significantly larger, deeper, and more accurate than they otherwise would have been.

THE ROUTINE PHASE of the mission started immediately after the commissioning review finished, on 18 July 2014. There was a bridging phase of a month or two where the scanning law was adjusted before the long-term 'nominal scanning law' was initiated.

Throughout the routine phase, 'station keeping', i.e. keeping the satellite in its intended orbit, uses radiometric data coming back from the ground stations. This

provides both Doppler (line-of-sight velocity) data, and range (distance) data. Using these over time allows flight dynamics to determine arcs of position and velocity over time whilst in contact with ground, using these to determine the orbit.

This is then modelled, propagated into the future, and then used to determine when station-keeping manoeuvres would have to be performed. These are short 'burns' of the satellite's chemical thrusters to adjust the orbit, and keep it within the intended L2 range. Initially this was done once per month, but later in the mission the adjustment period could be extended to once every two months or even longer.

WHILE THESE ARE conventional orbit determination techniques, the Gaia science demands an even better orbit reconstruction accuracy than could be achieved using standard procedures. Specifically, the accuracy required for the scientific performance (in object positions and proper motions) is to within 150 m for the position of the satellite, and within 3 mm/s (!) for the spacecraft velocity.

To achieve this, two other techniques were implemented. The first of these, 'Delta-DOR', essentially uses two of the ESTRACK 35-m antennae in parallel to perform interferometry. The second is based on ground-based telescope observations, with astronomers (led by the team in Heidelberg) taking images of the Gaia satellite against the background stars using ground-based telescopes. These two methods together yield sufficiently high accuracy in the 'plane-of-sky', for which the conventional radiometric techniques are insufficient.

ONCE INTO THE routine operations phase, operations generally ran much more smoothly. It could still happen that there would be a call in the middle of the night (or day) when some alarms trigger and are notified in telemetry. These could sometimes be rather trivial, and sometimes more serious, but over the years they certainly got less frequent. On the less serious side it can be that the data is not flowing into the control centre from the ground stations, and problems are found with the ground communications links that just need to be reconfigured or reset.

For the more serious problems, Gaia's safe mode will intervene and protect the on-board systems. This is not a frequent occurrence, having happened four times in total so far. Once the problem is understood, there are all the activities of switching the systems back, turning the spacecraft back to its normal rotation angle, and re-summing the spin rate.

This can typically require, say, 48 hours of active operations, followed by up to two weeks for the system to fully settle thermally to the levels demanded for Gaia's precise positional measurements.

APART FROM the failed chemical thruster noted previously, other issues involved a particle radiation ‘hit’ in the electronics of the cold gas thruster system, and an unrectifiable transponder failure albeit with a redundant unit that continues to work well. All problems are followed up rigorously, taking every measure to prove that it has been understood as fully as possible, and to mitigate any future occurrences. This could be, for example, by putting more autonomy onboard, or slightly changing operational mode. Such follow-up investigations might go on for many months.

GAIA IS AN extraordinarily sensitive telescope, and various tiny and unexpected effects have been identified during the course of the mission:

(a) Slight wobbles in the satellite pointing, orders of magnitude below what would be seen on a typical spacecraft, and duly identified as originating in the star trackers looking at particular parts of the sky. Eventually this was tied to errors in the star tracker’s ‘sky map’, which had its origins from the Hipparcos mission: the star tracker map included small errors, such as a reference single star actually being a double star, such that the centroid position was slightly displaced.

(b) Some other small attitude disturbances have been tied to tiny micro-meteorites hitting the sunshield, and causing slight spacecraft wobbling until the control system corrects it. Sometimes a thermal signature could also be observed on the sunshield, further localising where it had actually hit.

(c) A third type of effect are due to small bubbles in the chemical propulsion tanks slowly moving in zero gravity. Somewhat analogous to a lava lamp, small bubbles of propellant or oxidiser (or nitrogen) are moving around and settling after a station-keeping manoeuvre, the manoeuvre having pushed the fuel to one side of the tank after being executed.

(d) Finally, a small temperature drop on the sunshield was attributed to the appearance of a large sunspot. Remarkably, this could be identified as a result of the radiated power dropping very slightly.

FROM THE beginning of the project, we knew that particle radiation (mainly high-energy solar particles) could do considerable damage to the CCD detectors (mainly through ‘charge-trapping’) and to other payload elements, such as the computer and the onboard memory. We have recently been through Solar Cycle 24 (2008–19) and currently in cycle 25 (2019–30), fortunately with solar activity at some of the lowest for the past 150 years.

All CCDs continue to function nominally. There were some ‘switch downs’ over the past decade, of complete VPU rows or some effects at an individual CCD level due, for example, to radiation-induced ‘single event upsets’, but no permanent failures.

THE NOMINAL design lifetime, of 5.5 years, included 6 months for commissioning, followed by five years of nominal scientific operations. But the satellite included consumables for a possible extended mission for at least a further year... and even a 10-year mission was in at least some of our minds from the start!

The nominal 5.5 years of mission was reached in mid-2019. At that point, the operations team performed a relatively long and complex orbital manoeuvre to change Gaia’s trajectory so that the satellite would avoid going into the Earth’s shadow for a further 5 years.

The catalogue quality and content improves with increasing data. ESA’s science advisory committees have continued to rank Gaia very highly when considering extending operations. The onboard systems are working sufficiently well that around 10–11 years of operations should be possible in total. The ‘cold gas’ will run out in 2025, and with it the fine attitude control that Gaia needs to operate the telescope will no longer be possible.

TODAY, the Flight Control Team continues to perform the core operations. It is supported by other specialists at ESOC as needed, for example in the areas of flight dynamics, ground stations, and mission software.

In terms of personnel, the Flight Control Team currently comprises five engineers and an analyst, additionally taking a small share in the shift-working spacecraft controllers, the ‘Spacons’, who are also operating XMM and Integral in a shared team. Including the support sections this adds the equivalent of 2–3 more full-time staff.

I have based most of this account on my interviews with Dr David Milligan, 8 July 2022. As Gaia Spacecraft Operations Manager between 2008–2020, David was the leader of the team responsible for the operations of Gaia over the first seven years in orbit, a position subsequently held by Peter Collins.

Michael Perryman

The Gaia operations control room, used in the commissioning phase, ESOC, 3 June 2014. Left-to-right: David Milligan, Gary Whitehead, Peter Collins, Ed Serpell.